

CONTRIBUTION OF RELIGION TO SOCIETAL DEVELOPMENT IN BASSA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF KOGI STATE: PROSPECTS AND CHALLENGES

Okpe, Nicholas Ojoajogwu, Ph.D

Department of Religious Studies

Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba

Okpenicks@yahoo.com

And

Musa, Paul (Ph.D Student)

Department of Religious Studies

Prince Abubakar Audu University, Anyigba,

Paulmusa901@gmail.com (08080721341)

Abstract

The Role of Religion in Nigerian Society cannot be overemphasized, as they are evident in so many areas of Nigerian life. In various Nigerian societies, including the Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State, the practice of African Religion (AFREL), Christianity, and Islam is a reality, and this is part of the social institutions in Bassa society, as the three religious groups have lived in peace for centuries. They play various developmental roles. Therefore, this research aims to retrospectively look into the religious contents and contributions to the development of Bassa Local Government and the land. This religious contribution sustained the peace of society until three years ago, when it seemed that an inter-tribal clash between the Bassa and Ibira Koto had come upon the land. The research relies on Historical, Sociological, and Analytical approaches for data analysis, as both oral and written sources are adopted in the collection of data. The findings reveal the following contributions of Religion to Bassa land: spiritual and moral reshaping, education, health, political, and economic contributions. Also in the research are the challenges to the contribution of religion in Bassa Local Government Area, which are: reciprocative ideology, ethnic crisis, unemployment, characters of some political leaders, and denominationalism. All of these have been examined for the continued development of society, as it will be projected to achieve a better society.

Keywords: Religion, Societal Development, Bassa, Prospects and Challenges

Introduction

Bassa Local Government covers an area of 6 485 square miles. It was bounded on the north by the land west of the Rivers Benue and Niger, respectively. On the South by the southern Nigeria, and Muri province on the East” (Wabare 10). Thus, the society is made up of three major tribes, namely: Bassa-kwomu with one district and five wards, Bassa-Nge with one district and three wards, and Igbira Mozum with one district and two wards, making three (3) districts and ten wards, with Bassa-kwomu having the highest districts. The Local Government was founded in 1976.

Regarding occupations, the primary occupations of the people are farming, fishing, and craftwork. It has a large market square called the Sharia market where people from all areas of the state come around for buying and selling, especially food crops and fish. Some merchants travel from Nasarawa State to purchase food and fish simply because they are less costly compared to other places. It is a society that is more agriculturally oriented.

The three main religious groups in the Local Government have lived peacefully for decades. Christianity has the highest population, which is 50% while Islam has 30% and African Religion has 20%. These three major religions share a significant connection. However, some are syncretists. As the ethnic crisis erupted, the religious groups and other non-governmental organizations have been in control of it in order to foster the long-existing and enjoying peace of the land.

Religions in these areas have indeed positively impacted knowledge through education, reshaping the moral and spiritual lives of the people, as Well as Influencing Education, Health, politics, and other aspects of society. These have bonded the people together for an extended period of time, and they improve the economy of the society. Maintaining this good gesture for further development and peace is the goal.

A Brief History of Bassa Local Government Area and Religious Contributions

Bassa Local Government has been researched and discovered to fall in the Niger-Benue watershed. It is located between the institute 330 worth of the equator and longitude 60 30 and 70.5 East of the witch Meridian with an area of 233.735, 59km and population of over 107.001, (Local Government Survey Department). The Local Government has a population density of 5.4466 people per 59 km². According to Wabare, “Bassa Local Government Area covers an area of 6 485 square miles. It was bounded on the north by the land of the Benue and Niger rivers, respectively, on the South by Southern Nigeria, and on the East by Muri province.” (10). Omala Local Government also bounds Bassa Local Government Area to the east, while it shares a boundary with Dekina to the south. In the river

Benue and the western part is the Niger-Benue confluence. It has a moderate rainfall. The rain generally begins in the Local Government Area between March and April and extends to October/November. The climatic condition here is a Wara tropical savannah with several ally forests always along the river bank and in the interior.

Bassa Local Government Area is made up of three major ethnic groups with three districts. They are Bassa-Kwomu with a district and five wards, e.g, Akuba(1), Akuba (2), Ozongulo, Eyede, and Akakana, Ikende wards. The Bassa-Nge has a district with three wards: Gboloko, Kpata, and Oforo. In contrast, Igbira Mozum has a district with two wards: Mozum ward and Uzugbe ward, which comprise Bassa-Kwomu and Igbira Mozum. These three ethnic groups —Bassa-Kwomu, Bassa-Nge, and Igbira Mozum — have lived in harmony for years. They share things in common, speak each other's dialect. The Bassa ethnic group calls God, "Agwatana," while Bassa-Nge call God, Sokwo, and Igbira Mozum call God, Ihinegba. The Bassa-Kwomu ethnic group, according to some, originated from Egypt as they have the same burial culture as the Egyptians. Others observed that they originated from south-Africa particularly from the groups that do carry loads on their shoulders. Some scholars opine that the Bassa are from the Hausas mostly from the Kanuri group, and that they were cattle rarer before dumping the business and become full-time farmers; and have as a result of wars traveled and stayed in many parts of the country (Nigeria) including Kogi State.(Wabara 10).

The Bassa-Nge is believed to have come from the Nupe of Niger State and Patigi in Kwara State. They use the Nupe Bible version and claim to have migrated from Niger State. (Titus Jabunu Interview).The Igbira Mozum is said to have originated from Igala in Idah, and while othersopine that they are from Kakanda. These views are not concrete and convincing (Ogani Interview). The researcher believes that the opinions of many about the origin of some ethnic groups cannot be entirely accepted because they do not have a concrete basis. However, some ethnic groups do have some cultural affiliations in common with other neighboring ethnic groups.

Some activities form the socio-political life of the people; these are cultural settings, economic settings, and political settings. At one time or another, they meet together and share ideas; this also has projected the communal life of the people in the local government area. Culture is the total way of life of a people. It is a belief system of a group of people. Culturally, the three ethnic groups share a common culture of farming, eating, and drinking wine; these groups of people love coming together to dine, regardless of their spoken dialect. Farming for one another is also a culture or way of life among the people. The youths, heads of families, groups of women, and young ladies come together communally to work on the farm. One person's farm is visited today, and someone else's the next day or so (Rotational System). In doing so, they build each other's farm. Each person

to be visited is expected to cook for their visitors on the farm; this is a tradition found among the Bassa ethnic group in the Bassa Local Government Area. Some people get a job collectively and farm to save money, so at the end of the year, they can share the money or buy rice, meat, and drinks to celebrate, especially during Christmas. This portrays the unity of the inhabitants (Musa 24).

Economically, the ethnic groups engage in socioeconomically oriented occupations. This is generally true for the entire world; that is, every human being is involved in some occupation or another. Bassa-Kwomu are well known in farming systems, hunting, arts and crafts, while the Bassa-Nge and Igbira are well known for fishing, though some Bassa-Kwomu staying along the river line areas are also fishermen. These ethnic groups do farm, but not in the same way as the Bassa-Kwomu do. Some Bassas and Igbira Mozum do travel to the other side of the river in search of fish and trade them at key markets, such as Sharia, Aguma, Ikende, and Akanga. "Businessmen and women from Nasarawa, Lokoja, Dekina, and Abejokolo travel to Sharia market every five days to purchase food crops and fish, which they resell at other markets" (25-26).

The groups appoint leaders to lead, while others follow loyalty. The three ethnic groups have their traditional leaders who govern them in their districts. However, the traditional chairman of the council of chiefs resides at the headquarters (Oguma) in Bassa-Kwomu district. He heads the whole chiefs in the Local Government Area. The Bassa-Nge chief (ESU) and the Igbira Mozum (Ohiogba of Mozum) are all under the Aguma at the headquarters. They are to report to him and follow his instructions. Villages have their heads, known as Gagwu, and youth leaders who report to them. These village heads, in turn, report to the district heads, who also report to the Aguma at Oguma, the headquarters of the Local Government. Though all of these have to do with clans, where these heads must come from. The chiefs are selected by the kingmakers of a particular village (Jimba 29/11/2019).

During the installation of the new district head, the Aguma, who is the traditional council chairman, crowns the new head. Political leaders walk alongside a village head, the youth, and other groups to maintain law and order in society. The socio-political life of the Bassa people is sometimes informal and formal in its organization, as civilization develops within the society. The staying of the three ethnic groups together has brought much influence on the people of Bassa Local Government Area.

Religious Distribution

Bassa Local Government Area has three districts, as mentioned earlier. The religious distribution in Bassa Local Government, according to Mr. Shiloba, is as follows: Christianity accounts for fifty percent (50%) of the population. In comparison, Islam accounts for thirty percent (30%) of the population. In

comparison, African religion accounts for twenty percent (20%) of the population as of now. The Bass-Kwomu district is predominantly a Christian society, and the Bassa-Nge district is a mixture of both Christians and Muslims, while the Igbira-Koto residing in the Mozum district are predominantly Muslims, except for a very few non-Igbira persons residing amidst them. The other two districts have a limited mix of religions, but the Bassa-Kwomu district has a more diverse mix, mainly found in some remote villages. However, there is a problem of syncretism in all three of these districts, particularly regarding their religious practices. However, the concern of this paper is their relationship that leads to a contribution to the development of society (Kaku Interview).

The Christian Association of Nigeria (CAN) Bassa Local Government branch has worked well so far in fostering harmonious coexistence between the Christian body and other religious groups in the land. Therefore, they have sustained peace and tranquility in their creativity, whether in school, office, business, or elsewhere.

Religious Contribution (s) to the Area

The contribution of religion cannot be overemphasized, even when some seem to neglect the role of religion in their view, as they think religion is not capable of providing a solution to the problem of man in his physical and spiritual environment. Despite all the criticisms of religion, some have surrendered to religion as they are faced with metaphysical issues and meta-ethical issues. Smoke further says: "... the many other dimensions and impacts of religion tend to be downplayed or even neglected entirely (1). To prove this as a wrong mentality (Rowder in Enegho 23) submitted that: The early missionaries in West Africa had a dual purpose: to promote legitimate trade between Africans and Europeans and to convert Africans to their own religion. This came out clearly in the expedition up the river Niger in 1841. The object of this expedition, sponsored by the Society for the Abolition of the Slave Trade and for the Civilization of Africa, of which Buxton was a leading member, was to promote trade in the interior, to conclude treaties with local chiefs, and to establish a model agricultural farm. This farm, originally the idea of Commander William Allen, who had travelled with Laird's expedition in 1832, was to serve as an "expedition centre" for the surrounding people. The expedition, consisting of 145 Europeans, was given an official send-off at Exeter Hall by no less a person than Prince Albert, Consort of Queen Victoria (23).

The author pointed out that religion here plays a role in making a legitimate business; the conversion of Africans to Christianity establishes a model of an agricultural farm. Religion has positively brought about changes in the lives of the Bassa. The aspects of religious contribution to societal development in the Bassa environment are as follows:

- i. Spiritual and moral contribution, ii. Educational contribution, iii. Health contribution
- iv. Political contribution, v. Economic contribution

In respect to religious contribution, it is like what Jesus said in the Gospel of Matthew 6:33 when he says: “But seek ye first the kingdom of God and his righteousness; and all these things shall be added unto you” (KJV).

Spiritual and Moral Contribution

The African Religion (Indigenous religion), Christianity, and Islam have contributed significantly to the moral and spiritual lives of the people. Morality is a “system of moral standards based on principles of right and wrong” (Neill 349). “Morality cannot survive without religion, because of the vital role that religion plays as an agent of socialization of moral principle and values,” Iwe in (Ogbuehi 85). They go together, as morality is part of ethics, which judges the actions of a religious person. These religious groups have often taught their followers the moral principles and the importance of living a religious life, emphasizing the fear of God, who is believed to judge men on their activities, whether good or bad. According to (Shiloba Interview), “the moral and spiritual character of a child in the society is under watch for correction when an ill attitude is being displayed in the society” (Daudu Interview). Also commented that “religion in this environment has shaped the moral and spiritual lives of members of the milieu, as some evil acts are being minimized. He further said respect for elders has always been practiced by both children and youth in the Bassa Local Government. People in the land have felt the fear of God. The religious leaders of the three major religions often educate their adherents on moral conduct for a better citizenship. (Uye Interview).

Morality in every society is a code of ethics that cautions or moderates the ethos (character) of societal members. This adds to the spiritual teaching about relating to God as horizontal and to man as vertical. Wallah responded that, morality, spirituality so far kept the society save as people were guided by the code of conduct that when one offends God or the gods he or she was punished discovered in African Religion that even a chief of a community was punished by producing some cartons of beer or a big bottle of Burukutu (BKT), that is wine made out of Guinea Corn and a he-goat to spiritually cleans the village. However, this applies to everyone who commits a particular crime that warrants such punishment. Sometimes, when caught having sex with someone’s wife, serves such punishment. The reason for this is to spiritually and morally purify a community. This cautions members of a community against ill acts. (Ndazhaga Interview).

In a Christian church setting, a sin or immoral act that was worth church discipline was carried out. This is done by the church leadership temporarily putting outside a guilty member from communion service and other functional roles in the church pending when he/she confesses and repents of the wrong or sin he or she has committed. Upon their confession and repentance, the church council restores them gently, according to biblical injunctions. Then Christians establish Sunday schools, clubs, teen programs, and adult Bible study classes to spiritually and morally train adherents of their religious beliefs and practices, so they can maintain what they were born to meet as their religion. It is this quest for knowing more of God that moved Robert to start a bible school where people could learn the bible in concentration. This act also cautions members to live better in the church and in society (Gwatana Interview).

It is observed that in Islam, there are prayers and sometimes sacrifices are needed for the forgiveness of sins by Allah. In some cases, He punishes a guilty person, and when some sacrifices, either in the middle of the night or broad daylight, are offered along with the recitation of some Quranic verses, sins are forgiven. It is also important to note that in some cases Allah does not forgive some guilt but tortures or kills the offender, so this would always caution members of the society to live a spiritual and moral life (Usman Interview). To develop the spiritual and moral life of the people, some Muslims organized early morning and evening Quranic schools to teach children the Quran, where they learn more about Allah at the feet of the Mallam. Gbile and Noel said:

Robert had a burden and a vision to pursue. He had thought it all over, prayed and made plans. After building his small house at Akpaku, he set out to build a Bible School. The building was a small and was close to his house. He built a little house nearby where a young man, as well as two Bassa boys who were students and whose school fees he was responsible for, lived. The Bible school was to be a place where he could teach zealous young people from different parts and villages of Bassa (45).

The missionary's mindset was more focused on the spiritual life of the people, which was built on teaching the Bible and discipling new converts, regardless of their denomination. The author said: "Robert's commission was to produce saints, not men of great academic disciplines" (58). Spirituality and morality control religion for citizenship, though religion cloaks them. In Christianity, the spirituality and morality guide is pointed to the scripture, which contains both the Old Testament and the New Testament. This spiritual and moral manual has laws. It judges human standards by established laws for the betterment of man in human society. Renan said that "they are for all nations, and will remain the

commandments of God during all the centuries”, that is, the law is “for everyone and for all nations”. It is said that:

If God created this world, he must make some laws to govern it. In order to make life safe, we must have good laws; there is not a country that the sun shines upon that does not possess laws. Now this is God’s law, it has come from on high, and atheists and skeptics have to admit that it is pure. Legislatures nearly all over the world adopt it as the foundation of their legal systems (Moody 11).

The spiritual and moral code is found in Christian books and laws, as is also found in the Quran, to guide a nation. Therefore, religious contributions in terms of spiritual and moral standards reorganize the ethics (character) of the inhabitants of Bassa Local Government as they understand the tenets of the law. People can be seen living a mutual life with each other. The instructions from Christianity and Islam have reshaped society in respecting rulers and rulers also respecting their subjects. Also, the formation of a vigilante group for the community’s security is a mixture of traditionalists, Christians, and Muslims. The religious groups in the Local Government are attending spiritual programs like crusades, Molud, and some other religious activities.

The African traditional religious groups are without a written document, but transfer their code of conduct via oral communication as they pass from one generation to another. They are sometimes more spiritual and morally minded, as their punishment seems to be harsher than that of others in a physical sense. Africans aside, Christianity are highly morally sensitive people. So to promote spirituality and morality in African traditional religion, Idowu further explained that:

It maintains community unity and peace, for example in promoting submission of women and children, and respect for elders. It enforces everybody respecting rules and customs. It provides customs and ceremonies to pass on community history, tradition and culture. It enforces morality by punishing thieves, adulterers, greedy or selfish people. It forces people to fulfill their family responsibilities. For example, there are charms to stop thieves and calamities that befall the immoral. It gives relief from feeling of hopelessness in the face of illness, hostility, misfortune (such as drought) or fear of thee. People feel better when they think there is something they can do about the trouble. It gives relief from grief at separations when someone dies through supposed communication with the dead people are comforted if they feel they have a message from their dead father. The community also suffers some bad consequences demonic attacks and possession, and fear (13).

Religion purifies a community and reorganizes its activities, considering the consequence that follows disobedience of rules and regulations. It focuses on the

sanitation of a family, community, society, and the entire universe. Religion is not supposed to be partial in judgment. The political and moral function of religion has given hope to the hopeless, and it punishes the ill activities of men and women in the land. When attacked forcefully, some charms ward off certain ill activities of an enemy. Unity, peace, and progress are the heart's desire of every citizen. This spiritual and moral contribution of religion, however, is not without challenges or difficulties within and outside a religion.

Educational Contribution

Education is either informal or formal, and it is one of the social institutions that can change the perception of every society, though not all members are, in one way or another, influenced by the elites. Formal education is the “training received in a school, college, or university. This is the opposite of informal education” (Hornby 466). Before the advent of education, Africans already had means of acquiring education in various forms. Waruta in (Ogbuechi 81) maintains that there was no written language. Nevertheless, African people communicated their ideas through words, actions, and gestures. Children more often learn through apprenticeship and participation in the activities of the community.

The three major religions in the land from the beginning had informal education, and later formal education came through the advent of Christianity and Islam. Though formal education by Christianity and Islam in the land was so serious, the only target of the missionaries from both religions was to educate their followers on how to read and write (Kaku). Their concentration was on the Bible and the Quran. There was Bible School at Eyede, which was later moved to Odenyi by Robert Hyslop, a missionary to Bassa Land who operated from Bible Christian Fellowship. There was no emphasis laid on secular education, but on the spiritual and moral education. However, there seem to be changes today, as people continue to develop in their quest for knowledge. Some of these religious groups have today opened nursery and primary schools, as well as Secondary Schools, as part of their community development efforts. DMM Secondary School in Sharia by Roman Catholic Mission, Revival Fire Center Nursery/Primary School Nyenzhi, Faith Academy Nursery/Primary School Odenyi by Bible Christian Fellowship (B.C.F), Quranic school at Oguma, Bassa-Nge Anglican Grammar School Gbolok in Bassa-Nge district. Bassa-nge Community Secondary School, Adum-Woiwo, Assemblies of God Nursery/Primary School, Kpanche, Pleroma Nursery/Primary School, Kpanche, and others are New Jerusalem Nursery/Primary School, Agodo.

-Nursery/Primary School Koriko, Nursery/Primary School Oshuku by Akwu Idachaba

Nursery/Primary School Sharia, Nursery/Primary School Oguma.

The religious groups have made enormous contributions to the development of the land. The African religionists pass their educational activities through oral form (that is, for a primitive environment). They transfer teachings sometimes through practical means as the students decode. These religious contributions to education in the land are very significant to the land. Children have been able to develop intellectually. The education of society also includes farming, fishing, weaving, cooking, carving, and knitting: these were later developed by the indigenous missionaries. From the three major religions, as well as folktales, proverbs, poems, singing, and dancing, these cultural and educational elements were also integral to the society's cultural and educational system (Fafunwa 2). The educational contribution of religion has modernized activities that were previously considered local or has advanced some informal educational activities in the area; for instance, through schooling and training, agricultural activities have improved as people have learned about spraying and applying various insecticides to address problems. The religious contribution to education has today helped the Bassa Local Government, as they can now read and write.

Health Contribution

“Health is Wealth.” The religious groups, at different times, have established health centers for assisting the ill. Sometimes, doctors in the religious arena have introduced free medical treatment to cure some major and minor ailments in society. African religionists, Christians, and Muslims with the knowledge of herbs have cured illnesses using herbs in Bassa Local Government Area, examples: stepping on poisonous objects, strange headaches, stomach upset, incurable diseases by medical personnel and others. Some religious members visit hospitals to pray and sometimes donate money, clothes, food, and other items to the sick (Kaku Interview).

Audu says: “Regardless of one’s religion in the society, they visit whosoever has the solution to a particular illness. Muslims, Christians, and African religionists help each other with herbs; they share ideas to help cure some unusual illnesses. When serious illness seems to persist, they sacrifice whatever animal is accepted by the gods to inquire what is the cause of the problem and the possible solution. If need be, the sick person buys a hen, a cock, a pigeon, or whatever is demanded to appease the gods, and then proceeds to cure the sick, as the gods would be pleased. There could be a redirection on how to go about a treatment” (Interview).

In the case of Christians in Bassa Local Government, health issues are addressed through medical, herbal, and prayerful means. It depends on the situation of the sick, some Christians only believe in prayer, not medical support, and some believe in both prayers and medical assistance. In contrast, other believes in only medical support and herbs. There are categories of Christians in the Local Government Area. Some categories of Christians are good herbalists, and they

are: Audu Dangara at Odenyi, Joshua at Ankura in Oguma, Joel Shigiri of Gagba, Daniel at Idere along Akakana road, Emmanuel Ndazhaga at Kporo but residing at Anyigba, Abel Cheure at Kpanche, Rain at Sheria, Gweje Michael at Kpanche, Joshua Michael at Kpanche but resides at Jida-Bassa in Ajakuta Local Government, Michael Daudu at Kpanche, and many other Christians.

Muslims are like Christians in belief. Some believe in prayers, medication, and herbs, others believe only in herbs and medication, and to some, only in prayers and medication. Today, Muslims have introduced prayer houses as some spiritual illnesses are becoming alarming in society. In all, the religious groups have made enormous contributions to the health stability of people in society. Kudos to the understanding of the religious group. The efforts of these religious groups are to better society and complement government efforts.

Political Contribution

Religious leaders who are also politicians have made significant contributions to society. An officer has always come from one of these religions in the Local Government. They have contributed in raising mosque structure, church building, and supporting Christian Association of Nigeria's (CAN) programs, the chairman, secretary, cashier, treasurer and other officials sometimes comes from a Christian or a Muslim group Comrade Bako a politician observed that: Late Luke Shigaba, Late Matthew Jere, Late Musa Gwatana and others were christian's and Late Mallam Majida, Comrade Diche and others have served as Muslims on the Chairman's seat, and were committed religious leaders who served and supported the development of the society. They supported widows and widowers as part of the religious duties of a Christian and a Muslim, and provided secure jobs for some less privileged ones. The cabinet in the Local Government Area has enjoyed religious group activities in political hem and some have tried to do what is right. Although this was not without challenges and weaknesses, as is always part of human nature (Interview, 29/12/2019). Some Christians and Muslims have served as advisers to the chairman and other officials, and with the fear of God and moral ethos (character) have counseled the political leaders on what is right. Political leaders are also involved in the traditional ruler's activities of the land, this is evidenced in areas where some chiefs are almost pastors, devout Christians and Muslims; on this note, Umoh submits that politics: "Is the science and act of government, Government is the art of administering the affairs of the people. In every society, some political leaders govern the people. There are Kings, Queens, Oba, Emirs, Eze, and so on that make policies and ensure enforcement of these for peace and order to reign in society". (65).

In Bassa Local Government, there is the Aguma of Bassa in Oguma, the Esu of Bassa-Nge in Gboloko, the Ohlogba of Mozum, and other chiefs under them. The Aguma in Oguma is the traditional chairman of the council of chiefs. These are all

part of the government of the society that administers the affairs of the people. They all have political and religious roles for effective leadership, which some of them have been doing to develop their land. The Esu and Ohiogba from Gboko and Mozum districts report to the Aguma at Oguma, who serves as the chairman. Their clan heads report to them, while the two report to Aguma. All of these clan heads of the three districts, along with the chairman, participate in the politics of the land as they pray and bless political leaders to win elections or secure positions. These clans and district heads are either Christians or Muslims. Who prays for the good of the Local Government Area? The Afrel do not often show interest in a key political office at all levels, but are part of grassroots positions, and encouragers.

Religion, in relation to politics, has introduced justice, law, and rights, even though not in its perfect state. Some religious leaders in the helm of politics have ensured that laws are used as a means of protecting human rights and ensuring justice. They have made sure that laws are promulgated and made known to the general public before being enforced; laws may not be retroactive, that is, not extended past actions. Religious members in politics sought to ensure that laws are not contradictory or incompatible, as contradictory laws place citizens in a position where they cannot obey one law without violating another and incurring sanctions. Maintaining order is also a pursuit of religious groups with a political vision in the Local Government; this is to avoid confusion among citizens as a result of frequent changes in order (Peschve 149-151). This is common everywhere in the world where religious groups are actively involved in morally minded politics. This sanitizes the society. Religion, therefore, has excellent involvement in society as it has the power to reorganize and maintain law and order. Stressing further on this, Byrne says: "Even though a religion without a social dimension is not an acceptable religion because it is not relevant or meaningful. Religion can never be separated from life and realities of life that exist in society" (26). The author's projection that in an attempt to separate religion from a society, it means the society would cease to exist. They are together; they are one. The researcher, therefore, sees religion in a society as a manual guiding the activities of a society. It can be likened to a driver who drives a car before it can move.

Bassa Local Government Area is a productive society, because much of farming, fishing, craft-work, and businesses of different kinds take place there. Therefore, making the society a busy society. The religious contribution to the economy of the land cannot be over emphasized as the religious groups as individual has shops, Sawmill, large farm rice, fish ponds, group of hunters, grain dealers, vegetables, production which attract so many business men and women who travel from far and near to buy and sell, employing laborers; this activity contributes to the development of the Bassa Local Government Society.

Ruth, a respondent, said that: “Some people are being assisted financially in order to begin business irrespective of their religion, as they do that, there would be financial growth which leads to bigger investment and development of the society” (Interview). The economy has so far benefited from religious contributions. All aspects of religious contributions are embedded in the social institutions of a society. Therefore, religion is not stagnant or meaningless, but a strong foundation for a society, as a pillar to a gigantic building. This means religious contribution is like an engine in a car; a car can only move when an engine is ignited and functions well. Religion shapes society as members of a religious group either collectively or individually work to be good members of their society contributing to the welfare of their milieu, even in the face of challenges that are unavoidable when a society grows. Some Christians and Muslims embark on medicine, which involves the local felling of trees that were to be used for construction, and other activities. These are being exported outside the country. Villages where these operate are Orokwo, Ogodo, Edenye, Okudugu, Kpekere, Kporo, Inigwi-omono, Inigwi-Tamazhe, Gbogboligbo, Kubiri, Keteshi, Shemeje, Udogbo, Gboloko, Meguni, Shintaku, Emi-yakubi, Kpata Kpanche, Uwusa, and many more areas that have experienced the activities of operators who are into economic tree business, which the youths have always benefited from as they serve as contractors and transfers of the blanks from motorable forest daily living and other benefits.

Challenges to the Contribution of Religion

Despite the positive contributions of religion in Bassa Local Government, challenges have always accompanied societal development in the area. However, this is common in every developing society. The challenges to the religious contribution in the land are: Lack of reciprocative Ideology, ethnic crises, unemployment, some activities of politicians, and denominationalism.

Lack of Reciprocative Ideology

There is an adage in Bassa that says, “If a blacksmith finishes construction, it is left for you if you are not satisfied to contribute so it can be more perfect to your taste”. Therefore, this can be seen as an act of complementing what someone has done, but some people never saw the need to complement the efforts of religious groups in the Local Government Area. This challenge is one of the significant areas of concern that jeopardizes the religious contribution to society. Ali one of the elders in the community noted that some personalities do not invest into the economy of the land in order to complement what religious groups are doing to develop the society, some are well to do members in the society but hand closed to assist the less privilege in the area; and that in some cases they invest outside the community (Interview).

Among the religious groups, some have established Nursery/Primary schools, where pupils are taught and educated, and teachers are employed to earn their living. However, some do not establish such schools or other areas that complement what others are doing in respect to the development of their society. To stress further, Luke, during the interview, says “Some who benefited from religious groups do not see the necessity for doing good to other people around the society, having become successful in life”(Interview). Some seem to have forgotten the good done to them in order to extend the helping hand to others. William says:

God created you to make a specific contribution to the world and leave it better than you found it. Someone once said that everything you enjoy from the day you are born until you grow up is what other people have labored for. That is their contribution for coming before you. So you eat, play the roads, and fly the airplanes that others have invented. Nevertheless, if you leave all through your life enjoying those things and never make any contribution that other people after you will enjoy, you are a thief. This is because you are enjoying much but contributing nothing; only thieves behave that way; reaping where they did not sow (18-19).

William points at every man being purposefully created by God. That man is expected to live his society better than he/she met it, every humanity came to meet something done or created by others as contribution to their world, and therefore everyone is also to contribute; but this is a problem discovered by the researcher in some members lives in the Local Government Area which has hindered the progress and development in the society. The author’s idea of pointing out that people who refuse to contribute before their departure from the surface of this earth are considered thieves implies that they have lived and died without contributing to their society.

Ethnic Crises

Ethnic and Intra-Ethnic crises have sometimes caused a setback to societal development. The crises between the Bassa and Igbira Ethnic groups are one of the challenges affecting the religious development of the Bassa Local Government Area. The problem of not wanting the outing of Bassa masquerades during the death of a male traditionalist and the move to rotate the seat of the Traditional Council Chairman by the Igbira Ethnic Group is a long-standing, lingering problem that some religious groups and political leaders have tried to solve, but kept recurring. Mr. Shiloba submitted that the problem of the Igbira is related to the masquerade known as (Igenge), which only surfaces when a

traditionalist dies and has come to the position of having a masquerade out for his burial celebration. This Igenge is believed to be a dead person who comes temporarily and returns to the grave later. Therefore, throwing stones at him becomes a problem. Some who do not belong to this cultural activity hate it and in some cases throw stones at it; and sometimes see it as something to play with, this has always been the problem which escalates to ethnic crises. This has led to the dispersion of some inhabitants to other parts of the country, as the crisis erupted from a village called Kpanche in 2016 and was later reawakened on April 22, 2018 (Zhige Interview). The issue here is the lack of recognition of other people's cultural identity, which should always be respected, even in its plurality. Additionally, it has been observed that there is sometimes vagueness, confusion, and disagreement about people's practices within a society. An anonymous author says:

...racial categories are based on physical differences. The former focuses on "look", the latter on "outlooks". An ethnic group is a category of people who see themselves and are seen by others as distinct because of their cultural heritage. Ethnic groups are maintained by a "consciousness of kind" and the assumption that people who share the same ethnic background are likely to have similar values. Language and culture establish ethnic boundaries. Not only does "one's own wind" speak one's own language, but they speak it "correctly" food reference, traditional (or "folk") art, music and dance, religion, occupational specialties, family names, and a shared myth of the importance in establishing ethnic identity. (316).

The efficacy of culture binds a people that practice it, as its elements bring about a complete ethnic identity. In Bassa Local Government, this refers to the state of the Bassa ethnic group. The Bassa ethnic group consider the cultural identity of a masquerade coming out to mourn and celebrate the death of a male traditionalist as many activities would always take place like the site of the masquerade from related family members residential place within and outside the society, dressed with ethnic cachol, or ashes on the body, a carved wooden head, leaves on the waist to cover nakedness, a weapon like an arks, sword, bow and arrow, a catapult as they travel to the scene (that is from the world of the dead) to the world of the leaving and spent only two days; this is for those coming a far, but within the place of the scene it takes seven (7) days before the site is closed, and all the remnant masquerade return to the grave which is their ancestral home. During this time, sacrifices are made to the ancestors by a Chief Priest. In all the activities at the sacred site, women are forbidden to enter. Everything done by men is special, and is in the secret. This particular culture of masquerade is attached to the African Religion of the Bassa ethnic group. The crisis has affected the continuity of religious contribution in the land. Although religious bodies, including Christian,

Muslim, and African Religious groups, are praying for the crisis to come to an end, so that normalcy will return to the land.

There are three ethnic groups as said earlier. However, the Igbira ethnic group are seeking for the rotation of seat, this the Bassa ethnic group said it is impossible because it is their heritage not to be rotated among other ethnic groups, since it is the issue of clan not ethnic groups, for even among the Bassa ethnic group not all the clans in the land could ask for rotation of seat (Zhige Interview). This has been the desire of the Igbira ethnic group. The Bassa would always say all other ethnic groups are their guest, so how then should they share such a great traditional seat? This and many more have affected the past contribution of religious groups and the planned contribution, i.e., ethnic crisis affects the past, present, and future development of a society if nothing is done to curtail the unfortunate. The future of any society, in terms of development, lies in the peace of that society. African communities need to know where they have come from, where they are and where they are going and how it could look like, on this, Tubi submitted that: “Unless Africans learn of their past, they cannot comprehend their present nor plan for the future; until African know of their past, they will not be capable of construing the dynamics of the present nor be able to project into the future” (29). Tubi’s view is to encourage seriousness in African archaeological studies, which the researcher applies to the Bassa Local Government. He urges ethnic groups to look into the past, present, and future, so they can prevent ethnic crises and advocate for the development of the Local Government Area.

Unemployment

This has to do with a lack of a job, either private or public. Many graduates are unable to contribute to societal development. If they have payable jobs, they could do something to contribute to society's concerns. Individual or collective success can contribute to societal development. There are many educationists in various fields of endeavor in our society. Some of them are employed as religious teachers in mission and government-established institutions, while some are employed as medical doctors or engineers. Others were trained or ordained as religious leaders, evangelists, or preachers. These categories of people help to reduce the rate of unemployment and abate moral decadence in our society (Fabian in Okueze 113).

Fabian’s submission is the opposite of what has been experienced in Bassa Local Government Area, as unemployment is rated high in the area. Some have their diplomas, including the National Certificate in Education (NCE), Degrees, and the rest, but no job that would have encouraged participation in societal development. The problem of unemployment in the Local Government Area has introduced moral decadence and chaos, which affect the society’s wealth and structure instead of building it up. Idealness gives birth to evil, which in turn

affects other members of society. This therefore confirms Aquinas' statement in Okpe that: "... Nothing can be, except it is caused; thus, it could be inferred that evil, which is the absence of good, must have a cause resulting from some force" (100). This therefore points to the fact that some moral decadence activities and chaos are encouraged by a force that emanates from unemployment. This is because when one is busy doing something positive, society can have peace, and the result of public positive activities will benefit society.

Bassa Local Government Area is an environment that when youths and elderly members of the society are ready to work either employed by the Government or self employed can do better to increase and expand the resources of the land which in turn is capable of boosting the sustainable development of the areas. However, some seems to be too lazy as the Government does not employ them and still are not creative to embark on self employed jobs to take care of themselves and assist the society. Some do not just refuse to recognize what others are doing to develop society, but they are also lazy, dull, and weak in their work. Yet, they can sometimes be very judgmental and look up to the philanthropists of society. On this, Williams says: "... work is an avenue by which one fulfills God's plan and purpose for his or her life. There is nobody who is an accident on this planet. God created man to make a certain contribution to the world and leave it better than he met it" (18). So, unemployment caused by either the Government or oneself hinders the contribution of religions to the society's development. Okwueze stressed that: "The society is going crazy about religious music. These musicians have engaged themselves fully and have drastically reduced the number of unemployed in our Nigerian societies. Some radio and television programs are all geared towards making one cherish and foster in his daily life, common brotherhood under the "one eternal God," the "Father of All". Individuals are operating this program, and these individuals are paid for doing so" (113). Okwueze is pointing out an individual's involvement in doing one thing or the other, so one could earn their living and be a contributor to society's development.

Politicians and Their Activities

It has been observed that some politicians have also caused adverse effects on the continuous religious activities in society, including embezzlement of funds in various societies and organizations, which has also hindered the development of continuous religious activities in society. Some politicians have diverted public funds meant for social development, such as construction projects, assistance to widows and orphans, and support for the less privileged, secretly using those people's credentials and embezzling their salaries. The attitude, in turn, affects the social life of economic activities, spiritual/moral life, and psychological state of members of the society. History repeats itself, as it has been observed that during

the Roman world, there was political abuse of power regarding the economy of that period. It is on this note that (Gostsis and Oakman) in Ige comment that:

“The ancient Roman economy was political in two aspects: first, it was based upon forced extraction of goods through taxation of agricultural resources in the provinces, and second, it encouraged the movement of goods and commercial activities, in favor of the dominant elites or their delegates. This process resulted in an unequal distribution of property and riches, which led to economic exploitation through control. Hoarding and concentration of immense wealth by a small minority of the total population “(13). The political leaders are good at “extraction of goods through taxation...” and “encourage the movement of goods and commercial activities in favor of the dominant elites or their delegates.” Those in lowercarders do not do this.

Some of these politicians do away with what belongs to widows, orphans, physically challenged persons, and other material things. They rob the poor to become wealthy, though this is found everywhere in Nigerian society, but the concern of the researcher here is the Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State. The chairpersons, secretaries, directors, councilors, party chairpersons, ward leaders, and a lot more are not free from this epidemic that is affecting the contribution of religion to the Local Government Area. Some politicians have harmed many through social injustice, abusing power and wealth. Every world has this challenge, as some are working to curb the ill execution of power. In explaining further on some politicians' activities, Malina asserts that: “A person could not accumulate wealth except through the loss and injury suffered by another. A fourth-century Mediterranean proverb says: “Every rich person is either unjust or the heir of an unjust person”, or every rich person is a thief or the heir of a thief.” The outlook was the same in the first century” (104).

Suppose politicians put a hold on corruption and release the releasable. In that case, society will experience growth and development as they give to the poor what belongs to the poor, and the rich what belongs to the rich. The encouragement of crisis by some politicians is another challenge that the Bassa Local Government Area is facing. It is on this note that Okwueze submitted that: “The central point in all religions is moral, and those who do not keep the commandment do not promote the cause of the gospel in society. Religions, when positively used, promote the political life of any society. In the face of war, oppression, and tyranny, there can be no development in politics, economics, and religious life of the society. War always leads to the destruction of natural and human resources, hunger, and illness” (113). This is because it has been investigated and discovered that some of the wars in various societies are politically motivated and sponsored under the disguise of religion and an ethnocentric agenda.

Denominationalism

According to Hornby, denomination is “a branch of the Christian church: the feeling that you are better or more important than other people (923). It is a religious organization that has a positive relationship with society and accepts the legitimacy of other religions. Like an established church, it is at ease with the norms, values, and practices of society. Nevertheless, unlike either an established church or a sect, it does not claim to have “the answer”. Not claiming unique legitimacy, the denomination views religious participation as a voluntary activity. (N.N. Sociology: An Introduction, p. 491).

Denominationalism in society is an agent of setback in and outside religious settings. She is expected to value other organizations, norms, and practices of a society, pray for other denominations, not see herself as superior to others, not think she has the best doctrine and being at the top, some denominations do not show any act of love towards others around them. They conclude on their judgmental view or opinions and look down upon other denominations, and would not want to fellowship with other denominations. The denomination encompasses Christian denominations, Islamic groups, or intra-Islamic groups which sometimes form sectarian groups. Their leadership sometimes is hateful, brutal, harsh, and destructive, but still claim to be a religious group. According to Edwards in (Alexander 61)

Love does not “cherish inflated ideas of its own performance,” in other words, love does not have a superiority complex. This was an important concept for Jesus’ disciples to understand because many of the religious leaders of their day were puffed up with religious pride. One self-inflated Pharisee was observed praying to himself: “God, I thank you that I am not like other men” (Luke 18:11)... I have written something to the church, but Diotrephas, who likes to put himself first, does not acknowledge our authority. So if I come, I will bring up what he is doing, talking wicked nonsense against us. And not content with that, he refuses to welcome the brothers and also stops those who want to, putting them out of the church. (3John 9-10).

. There are numerous religious denominations, but some proudly promote their own denomination. Sometimes, some preach and teach their church doctrines, leaving out the texts being read. This has also been discovered among many denominations in the world, being Christian denominations, intra-Islamic groups, or sects.

Recommendation

The researcher suggests that Bassa Local Government inhabitants should understand and respect one another's ethnic and religious groups for peace and sustainable development in the society. The researcher also recommends that spiritual and moral practice in the Local Government Area should be maintained, because any society where spiritual and moral teachings and practice are not held, the freedom and peace of such a society are at stake. It keeps a society running smoothly, sanitized, and pure, as it respects the religions in the land. Education is the bedrock of every society; therefore, it must be maintained, and more schools should be established, along with other educational programs in the Local Government Area, for sustainable development. The religious groups and other individual are employed to see the efficacy of education in their areas.

Health is the people's wealth, and it must be encouraged and taken seriously by creating more health centers, herbal homes, and genuine prayer houses for spiritual illnesses. Groups of any faith should not be too extreme to the point that they would not be able to be sensitive to illness that is medical and illness that is spiritual, which will need the attention of either one to intervene.

Conclusion

The research work has focused on the Contribution of Religion to Societal Development, a case study of Bassa Local Government Area of Kogi State, in particular, and as found in the entire world. It is very clear in the work that ethnic and religious groups have made enormous contributions to the development of Bassa Land, as individual and collective groups have played vital roles in society. Religious contributions in Bassa land encompass spiritual, moral, educational, health, political, and economic aspects, which have organized and given a new shape to the lives and practices of the people, as they caution people's lifestyle in relation to one another, even in the face of challenges. The Christians, Muslims and African Traditional Religionists are involved in the development of the society through spiritual and moral teachings that guide the people, and their establishment of schools beginning from Nursery/Primary schools, Private Secondary Schools, and Tertiary Institution notably the Unity College of Education at Odenyi which is an extension program from Aukpa, Adoka in Benue State through Yakub Obed and Musa Paul in the year 2016 as part of community development which has her first graduates in 2019.

Works Cited

- Alexander, Strauch. *A Christian Leader's Guide to Leading with Love*. Colorado: Lewis and Roth Publishers, 2006.
- Armin, W. Geet, and Randi. Warne (ed). *New Approaches to the Study of Religion, Vol. 1: Regional, critical and Approaches, Berlin, New York: de Gruyter, 2000*
- Enegho, F.E. *German Missionaries and their Impact on Christianity in Nigeria, 1842- Ilorin: 2017.*
- . . .Nigeriacentrism: Pathways of Religion and Culture. Ilorin: Nathadex Publishers, 2013
- Fafunwa, A.B. *History of Education in Nigeria*. Ibadan: NPS Educational Publishing Limited, 1994.
- Fuller, Lois. *A Missionary Handbook on African Traditional Religion*. Bukuru Press & Publishers Ltd, 2001.
- Gbile, A., and Noel, D. A. *Bassa Heart. Robert Hyslop spent 32 years serving the Lord in Nigeria*. Gboko: Peace House Press Team, n.d.
- Idowu E.B. *African Traditional Religion: A Definition*. London SCM Press, 1983.
- Ige, A.S. *Introduction to the World of the New Testament*. Lagos: Tokem Prints, 2019.
- Karl, H.P. *Christians' Ethics: Moral Theology in the light of Vatican II Vol. 2*. Bangalore: Theological Publication; India, 2004.
- Mbiti, J.S. *African Religion and Philosophy*: London: Heinemann, 1969
- Moody, D.L. *Weighed in Balances'* Dromore: revival Publishing, 2012.
- Nmah, P.E. *Basic and Applied Christian Ethics: An African Perspective*. Onitsha: Gucks Systems International, 2012.
- Ogbuehi, Friday I. *Essentials in the Study of Religion*. Nsukka: Chuka Educational Publishers, 2018.
- Okpe, N.O. *The Quest for God (Good) Amidst Evil in the World Today*. Saarbrücken: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing, 2017
- Okwueze, M.I. (ed) *Religious and Societal Development*. Lagos: Merit International Publications, 2004.
- Ethics, Religion, and Society. Nsukka: Prize Publishers, 2003

Tubi, Paul-Kolade. *Introduction to Archaeology of Africa: A Beginners' Handbook*. Lokoja: Plain Truth Publications, 2017.

Umah, B.U. *A Religion, Politics, and Society in Okon Reading in the Scientific Study of Religion*. Calabar University of Calabar Press, 2011.

Wabare, Paul. *The Bassa Speaking People of Nigeria*. Ahmadu Bello University Press, Ltd, 1993.

William, Okoye. *You are Created for a Higher Purpose*. Garki: Integrity Publications. 2002.

William,. *You are Created for a Higher Purpose*, Garki: Integrity Royal Publications, 2002. Okoye

Journal and Unpublished Materials

Malina, Bruce J. "Religion in the Imagined New Testament World; More Social Science Lenses, *Scriptura International Journal of Bible, Religion and Theology in Southern Africa* 51 (1994); 104.

Musa, Paul. *The Advent of Christianity and Its Impact on the Inhabitants of Bassa Local Government Area, Kogi State (A Postgraduate Project Submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, Kogi State University, Anyigba, 2015)*.

Okpe, N.O. "Religion as a Catalyst of Nation Building in Nigeria " *Journal of Social Sciences* Vol. 2.72, June 2014.

N. N. *Local Government Survey Department*.

Dictionaries

Hornby, A.S. *Oxford Advanced Learners Dictionary*. New York: Oxford University Press, 2000.

Karen D. et al. *The Students' Bible Dictionary*. Barbour: Holman Bible Publishers. 2000.

Neil, Mary O (E.D). *Chambers Students' Dictionary*. Edinburgh: Chambers Harrap Publishers Ltd, 2006.

Internet Sources

Dictionary. Com [www. Dictionary. Com/ browse/religion](http://www.Dictionary.Com/browse/religion).

Oxford Dictionaries. [https://www.oxforddictionaries.com/ Com religion](https://www.oxforddictionaries.com/Com religion).

Table of Oral Sources

NAME	AGE	ADDRESS	DATE
Angulu, Ali	45	Central Mosque Edenye	30 th August, 2019
Daudu, Luke	40	Faith Academy Nursery/Primary Sch.	1 st August, 2019
Dogwo, Mark	65	Warrior Christian Assembly Oguma	29 th November, 2019
Gwatana, Stephen	63	Bible Christian Fellowship, Gbedikere	30 th November, 2019
Jimba, Tukura	65	Behind Sheria Market Square	29 th November, 2019
Kaku, Stephen	67	Bible Christian Fellowship, Oguma	5 th December, 2019
Ndazhaga, Daudu	68	Behind Revival Fire Ministry, Kporo	3 rd October, 2019
Ruth, Gwatana	38	Zion Chapel	4 th September, 2019
Shiloba, S. John	67	CCM, Oguma	1 st September, 2019
Usman, Mathew	60	CEFN Church, Oshuku Bassa LGA	3 rd October, 2019
Uye, David	54	Opp. Bible Christian Fellowship, Eyede	4 th September, 2019
Zhige, Isaac	55	Opp. Assemblies of God Church Kpence	1 st December, 2019

